

DEVELOPMENT OF FOAM CORE SANDWICH PANEL STRUCTURE FOR TRANSPORT NOSE COMPONENT

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SUMMARY: Research activities have been conducted since 1999 to develop a new technology for the nose structure application of civil aircraft. Utilizing innovative materials and new engineering design concept, it is estimated that the application to the aircraft nose structure will reduce 20% in weight and 80% in parts count. The conventional nose skin panels are comprised of skins, stringers and frames, and they will be replaced by CFRP sandwich panels, namely CFRP surface skins and foam cores. The engineering feasibility of CFRP sandwich materials to the aircraft application has been established through several coupon tests. These tests have included but not limited to coupon core splices, static, fatigue tests, and bird strike test on the inclined flat panel. In addition, to ensure that the new technology meets the Federal Aviation Regulation (FAR) requirements, several sub-component tests have already been conducted and a full-scale test of the nose structural component is under way. Finite Element analysis has played an important role to determine the deformations and stress concentrations around discontinuities, especially in the open window regions. All these information are vital to ensure a successful full-scale test. Through these activities, the utilization of innovative material and new engineering design concept to the aircraft nose structure has been established.

KEYWORDS: Carbon matrix composites, Cost-effective implementation, Industrial applications, Integrated design and manufacturing, Structures

INTRODUCTION

A good prospective has been established to achieve weight and parts count reduction through the application of the new technologies. These technologies are in the area of composites, precision castings and Friction Stir Welding and they are all applied to the nose structure through this research activity. [1],[2]

Only the research activity on composite technology is presented in this paper. Though a composite structure has an advantage of a weight reduction, relatively high level of production cost compared to the metallic structure hampers a wide spread usage of this material. In order to improve, an adoption of an innovative structural concept is essential as well as automatic fabrication process. A new structural concept of the Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) sandwich panel with synthetic core to the aircraft nose skin panel has been used. The nose of transport category aircraft is a tri-dimensional complicated built-up structure. Though there is much room to reduce fabrication cost, few efforts have been conducted in the past. Through this research, the co-cured CFRP sandwich panel technology is to be developed and applied to the aircraft structure in order to reduce its structural weight and parts count.

Conventional honeycomb core sandwich panel has the disadvantage of water entrapment. In order to overcome this defect, synthetic core sandwich panel is selected.

The numerical target of our research is to achieve a 20% weight reduction and an 80% parts count reduction through these applications compared to a baseline airplane. As the baseline

airplane, an existing transport was selected.

This paper mainly describes the structural design and analyses of nose component and experiment results of data acquisition tests.

DEVELOPMENTAL PLAN

Our research plan consists of two phases, namely “the basic technology establishment phase (1999-2001)” and “the structure engineering verification phase (2002-2003)”.

In the basic technology establishment phase, a preliminary design, material characterization tests and process tests will be conducted in order to assess engineering application feasibility. Material allowable tests, design development test and point design allowable test were already conducted in this phase. As for the composite material, core splice tests, a structural element test of sandwich panel joint, impact damage tests and bird impact tests have also been conducted.

In the structural engineering verification phase, design and verification tests of a full-scale nose structure will be performed in order to show compliance with the Federal Aviation Regulation (FAR) Part 25.

Prior to the full-scale test, subcomponent test of sandwich panel joint under pressurization was conducted.

STRUCTURAL DESIGN AND ANALYSIS

1. Design

A complex built-up metallic structure was replaced by a simple sandwich panel. This panel consists of 180 centigrade degree cured CFRP surface skins and foam core. [1]. The structural concept is shown in Fig.1

The nose skin panel consists of an upper sandwich panel and a lower sandwich panel. Each sandwich panel was divided into two parts, right hand-side and left hand-side for the production efficiency,

since one-piece large panel is expected to have more problems in production, such as difficulty in the lay-up process. These panels are jointed with flush butt splice backed up by a metal beam. The joint concept was selected due to an easy visual inspection.

Fig.1 Structural Detail of CFRP Sandwich panel

Fig.2 Detail design of the nose

Fig.3 Detail design of the panel joint

These metallic beams named longitudinal beams for the panel splice are used as the current flow path in case of the lightning strike. The effect of a thermal stress was also investigated and no significant effect was confirmed.

The detail design of the nose structure is shown in Fig.2.

As a joint concept, a flush butt splice joint concept was selected from the inspection and assembly point of view. The flush butt splice is shown in Fig.3.

2. FEM analysis

Considering the above concepts, the detail design of the nose structure was carried out and the Finite Element Method (FEM) analysis was conducted for the critical loading conditions of a pressurization load and landing loads. Through this analysis, it was confirmed that the pressurization load was sustained by the CFRP sandwich panels and the local bending moment due to open sections like a windshield cutout was also sustained by the rigidity of the sandwich panel. The result of the FEM analysis is shown in Fig.4.

Fig.4 FEM analysis Result

3. Joint analysis

The detail FEM model of the panel joint was made and the design allowable of the joint was obtained through the structural element tests

The strain behavior of the sandwich panel joint is shown in Fig. 5.

The analysis tells us the high level of strain at the edge of the foam core.

Fig.5 Strain Distribution of Panel

4. Stress analysis of nose structure

Based on the internal loads obtained by the FEM analysis, stress analyses were carried out. The analyses of all parts of the nose structure had enough margin of safety and the minimum figure was 0.04 at the connecting point of sandwich panels and windshield frame. (See Fig.6)

Based on the detail design, 23% weight reduction and 98% parts count reduction was estimated for the composite parts. This result meets our numerical target of 20% weight reduction and 80% part count reduction.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

1. Core splice test

The core of the sandwich panel is comprised of several small cores with the size of 1meter by 1meter. Each core is spliced with a foam tape adhesive. Therefore, the strength of the core splice portion was obtained through the tests.

The four point bending tests of the core splice parts were conducted as a supporting data. The test results were shown in Table I.

The table shows that the core strength of both types of splice has no significant difference. Therefore, it has been confirmed that the core splice does not lead to the core strength degradation.

Table I Core splice test results

	Specimen	Average Strength	Remarks
Compression strength (MPa)	With a splice	143	
	Without a splice	149	

2. Structural element test for panel splice joint

Relating to the sandwich panel joint, the internal strain distributions were obtained through the FEM analysis. In order to estimate the joint strength, it was necessary to confirm a fracture mode and fracture strain of the joint. Therefore, the structural element tests of the panel joint were conducted. (See Fig.7)

The strain – load diagram is shown in Fig.8. In this diagram, the occurrence of the initial crack indicated an abrupt change of the curve in the strain gage C. The gage

Fig. 7 Structural element test status

locations are shown in Fig.9. Based on the test data, FEM analysis was modified in order to predict the crack initiation point in the uni-axial loading condition.

Fig.9 Strain gage locations

Fig.8 Load – Strain diagram of joint

3. Subcomponent test for the panel joint

As for the sandwich panel joint design method, the fracture mode and fracture load of the joint under the uni-axial loading condition is estimated through the structural element test.

Prior to the full-scale test, structural test of the sandwich panel joint under pressurized loading condition should be necessary in order to obtain more precise prediction of the failure.

To obtain the load distribution vicinity of the joint simulating the actual condition and confirmation of the joint strength, subcomponent test was conducted.

The test article simulates the joint portion of the sandwich panel. (See Fig.10)

This test article with strain gages was set to the test fixture. (See Fig.11)

The pressure loads were applied with a hydraulic pressure. The strain and displacement near the joint portion were measured. The set-up of the test article is shown in Fig.12.

Fig.10 Test article of the subcomponent test

Fig.11 Test article installation

Fig.12 Set-up of the test article

Limit load of 74.6kPa is set as the pressure differential loads corresponding to the maximum relief valve setting multiplied by a factor of 1.33 according to the FAR 25.365 (d).

Limit load test, ultimate load test (limit load multiplied by 1.5) and fracture test were conducted in the subcomponent test.

The relation between strain and pressure for the gages located on the panel centerline are shown in Fig.13. In limit load test of 74.6kPa loading and ultimate test of 111.9kPa loading, the linear relation between strain and pressure was confirmed. No residual strain and permanent deformation were also confirmed. In the fracture test, the crack initiation at the core edge was occurred at the loading condition of 380 kPa. The crack initiation was confirmed by the abrupt change of the strain – pressure relation in data of the strain gage 009 (See Fig.13).

Fig.13 The relation between strain and the pressure at the panel centerline

The similar result was obtained through the strain data at 120 mm offset from the panel centerline. (See Fig.14)

In this diagram, the crack initiation was slightly delayed comparing to the results shown in Fig14. This phenomenon indicates the crack propagation direction shown in Fig.15

Fig.14 The relation between strain and the pressure at 120 mm offset from the panel centerline

Through the structural element test and subcomponent, the fracture mode and fracture load of the joint were identified. Based on these data, FEM analyses are to be modified for more precise prediction. The accuracy of the analyses will be confirmed through the full-scale test to be conducted the end of 2003. Through these activities, the design method and procedure of the sandwich panel joint will be expected to be established.

4. Hail attack test [4]

The static and fatigue tests of damaged specimens due to the hail attack have been conducted, and it was possible to obtain the design data.

The relation between the energy level and the hail attack damage is shown in Fig.16.

No significant damage could be detected with a visual inspection. Through these tests, the damage characteristics of the CFRP sandwich panel have been obtained. The static test data is shown in Table II.

These fracture loads were much higher than those of applied load during the operation. Therefore, no significant effect of the hail attack damage was confirmed.

The fatigue test data were shown in Fig.17. Through these tests, the endurance of more than 10^6 was above the half of the fracture load. If the fracture load equals to the ultimate load, the half of the fracture load corresponds to the operational load. So, these test results tell us that the damaged structure has good fatigue property under the operational loading condition. Though the final endurance characteristic should be estimated for the actual load spectrum, the prospect of the endurance against the damage was obtained. [3]

Table II Static Test Results

	Average Value (N=3)	Standard Deviation	Cv (%)
Damage A	126 MPa	1.54	1.23
Damage B	125 MPa	4.58	3.66
Flaw	153 MPa	2.28	1.49

Damage A: 2.5Dia inch Hail attack Damage.

Damage B: Tool Damage of 0.1in depth.

Flaw: 0.75in *0.75in flaw

5. Bird impact test [4]

In order to obtain the design data for bird strike damage and later to validate the analytical method, bird strike tests of flat CFRP sandwich panels has been conducted.

Fig.15 Crack propagation direction

Fig.16 Damage Characteristic Test Results

Fig.17 Fatigue Test Result

Fig.18 Damaged test article

Two types of sandwich panel test articles were selected and tested. One had 4ply $[(45, -45)/(0,90)]_2$ surface skin and the other had 8 ply $[(45, -45)/(0,90)]_4$ surface skin.

The tests have shown that both articles could sustain 4-pound dummy bird impact at 320 kts velocity. The test article with 4-ply skin after the impact is shown in Fig.18 and the dent distribution due to the impact is shown in Fig.19.

Based on these data, 4-ply skin has been selected for the critical areas against the bird strike.

The boundary condition of the test article has a significant effect on the damage characteristics. This information is valuable to validate and adjust the FEM model. By comparing the test data with the analytical model, the effect on the boundary condition of the test article will be estimated and the strength against bird strike will be predicted. [3]

6. Full-scale test plan

As for the full-scale component test, a study of the test article configuration and test plan will be conducted. The fabrication process of the nose sandwich panel was also conducted. Through the process, the skin panels of the test article were fabricated. The size of the full-scale test article has 3.5m diameter and 3.5m long.

The upper half portion of the nose skin panel is shown in Fig.20. Assembly and verification test will be performed the end of 2003.

Fig.20 Nose skin panel (Upper half)

The full scale component will be conducted under the static loading condition of the limit load test and the ultimate load test. The objectives of the test are to validate static strength of the foam core sandwich panel structure and obtain the test data to compare to the analytical result of the joint portion. In order to obtain the suitable data, the strain gages and the potentiometer for displacement will be installed mainly to the joint portions. The test load will be applied with a pneumatic pressure with an air compressor.

The test set-up is shown in Fig.21.

Fig.21 Full scale component test

CONCLUSION

Through the research activities from 1999 to 2003, the following results are obtained.

1. Nose structural design was finalized. Sandwich panel design method including joint design method was established.
Through this design, our numerical targets of the 20% weight reduction and 80% part-count reduction can be achieved for a composite structure.
2. Design data of the sandwich panel such as joint and core splice were obtained through the structural element test and the subcomponent test.
3. Design procedure of the sandwich panel are investigating.
4. Large size sandwich panel fabrication process was established through the fabrication of tool try article.
5. Full scale structural test plan was prepared.
6. Fabrications of the nose skin panel are conducting.

Based on these results, the next phase of the structural engineering verification phase will be proceeded. Our final goal is to confirm the validity of our design through the full-scale nose structural test.

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